

Condensation with *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde : The condensed product on recrystallisation with petroleum spirit was found to be 1-benzoyl-1-phenyl-2-(*p*-nitrophenyl) ethylene, m.p. 89° (Found, N, 3.8; C₂₁H₁₅NO₃ requires N, 4.2%). Maximum yield 60% of the condensed product was obtained when the reactants were heated for 12 hours at 160° in the presence of a mixture of pyridine and acetic anhydride as the condensing agent.

Condensation with *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde : The condensed product on crystallisation from petroleum spirit was found to be 1-benzoyl-1-phenyl-2-(*o*-nitrophenyl) ethylene, m.p. 150°. (Found, N, 3.6; C₂₁H₁₅NO₃ requires N, 4.2%). Maximum yield 60% of the condensed product was obtained when the reactants were heated for 6 hours at 160° in the presence of a mixture of pyridine and acetic anhydride as the catalyst.

Condensation with 5-bromosalicylaldehyde : The condensed product on crystallisation from alcohol acetone mixture was found to be 1-benzoyl-1-phenyl-2-(2'-hydroxy-5'-bromo-phenyl) ethylene, m.p. 115°. (Found, Br, 20.9; C₂₁H₁₅BrO₂ requires Br, 21.1%). Maximum yield 98.5% of the condensed product was obtained when the reactants were heated for 6 hours at 160° in the presence of piperidine as the catalyst.

Condensation with 3 : 5-dibromosalicylaldehyde— The condensed product on crystallisation from alcohol acetone mixture was found to be 1-benzoyl-1-phenyl-2-(2'-hydroxy-3' : 5'-dibromo-phenyl) ethylene, m.p. 105°. (Found, Br, 34.6; C₂₁H₁₄Br₂O₂ requires Br 34.9%). Maximum yield 85.6% of the condensed product was obtained when the reactants were heated for 6 hours at 120° in the presence of piperidine as the condensing agent.

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Studies on Solvation of Ions in Nonaqueous Media : Part-I. Whether the Apparent Molal Volumes of Strong Electrolytes in DMSO is an Additive Property ?

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IN our previous studies¹, apparent molal volumes of some 1 : 1 electrolyte e.g. NaBr, NaI, NaNO₃, KBr, KNO₃, CsI and R₄NI (R = CH₃⁺ to C₇H₁₅⁺) have been reported at different concentrations and the values of limiting apparent molal volume, ϕ° , have been obtained by the extrapolation of almost straight lines ϕ_v vs $|\bar{C}$ curves to zero concentration. The results were discussed in the light of solute-solvent interaction. Due to limited data in DMSO, it was not possible and justified at that time to test the additivity of limiting apparent molal volume in this solvent. It may be mentioned here that the ϕ° values of electrolytes are found to be additive in solvents of high dielectric constant and strong hydrogen bonding like water², formamide³ and N-methyl propionamide (NMP)^{4,5}. Dimethylsulphoxide differs much from these solvents, having no hydrogen bonding and the dielectric constant ($\epsilon_{25^{\circ}} = 46.6$) is also much lower than the above group of solvents. Therefore, it seems quite desirable to test the additivity of ϕ° of electrolytes in DMSO before evaluating limiting ionic molal volumes to have a more clear picture of ion-solvent interaction in DMSO. Keeping this in view, apparent molal volumes of few more 1 : 1 electrolytes, namely, KI, CsBr, NH₄Br, NH₄I, NH₄NO₃ in DMSO have been determined at different concentrations and temperatures. The ϕ° values have been obtained from the ϕ_v vs $|\bar{C}$ curves and the additivity is tested.

Experimental

The salts used were all of B.D.H., A. R. grade, except NH₄I which was of U.S.S.R. pure grade. These salts were further purified by repeated crystallisation from conductivity water before use. The purified crystals were dried to a constant weight in a hot air oven and kept in a vacuum desiccator. The rest of the experimental procedure for determining density and calculating the apparent molal volumes therefrom was the same as detailed earlier⁶.

Results and Discussion

From the ϕ_v data, ϕ_v vs $|\bar{C}$ curves were drawn for various salts at different temperatures. These curves were almost linear with a positive slope for all the salts studied here, similar to those for the other common salts reported earlier¹. By the extrapolation of these straight lines to zero concentration, limiting apparent molal volumes, ϕ° , are obtained for various salts at

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different temperatures. The ϕ° values thus obtained are given in Table 1, along with the corresponding values for other common salts reported earlier¹.

TABLE 1—LIMITING APPARENT MOLAL VOLUMES OF SOME COMMON SALTS IN DMSO AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Salts	ϕ° in ml mole ⁻¹ at					
	35°	40°	45°	50°	60°	70°
NaBr*	19.14	18.82	18.55	18.20	17.22	16.54
NaI*	35.65	35.42	34.92	34.40	33.72	33.15
NaNO ₃ *	27.94	—	27.70	27.30	25.76	23.85
KBr*	24.65	25.40	26.25	25.90	25.00	23.24
KI	40.99	41.54	41.44	40.74	39.79	38.73
KNO ₃ *	33.70	33.85	—	33.32	32.46	30.72
CaBr	30.52	31.09	31.57	30.92	29.82	28.13
CaI*	46.92	47.75	48.05	47.92	47.25	45.94
NH ₄ Br	34.10	34.25	33.75	33.30	32.70	31.65
NH ₄ I	50.55	50.15	49.50	48.80	47.95	46.80
NH ₄ NO ₃	42.80	43.00	42.90	42.50	41.80	40.10

*Values for these salts have been taken from our previous communication (1)

Additivity of limiting apparent molal volumes of salts in DMSO :

The additivity of ϕ° values given in table 1, has been tested in table 2.

TABLE 2—ADDITIVITY OF ϕ° OF SALTS IN DMSO AT 35°

(1) $X(\phi^{\circ}KX - \phi^{\circ}NaX)/cm^3 \text{ mole}^{-1}$	Selected values
Br ⁻	5.51
I ⁻	5.34
NO ₃ ⁻	5.76
(2) $X(\phi^{\circ}NH_4X - \phi^{\circ}NaX)/cm^3 \text{ mole}^{-1}$	
Br ⁻	14.96
I ⁻	14.90
NO ₃ ⁻	14.86
(3) $X(\phi^{\circ}NH_4X - \phi^{\circ}KX)/cm^3 \text{ mole}^{-1}$	
Br ⁻	9.45
I ⁻	9.56
NO ₃ ⁻	9.10
(4) $M(\phi^{\circ}MI - \phi^{\circ}MBr)/cm^3 \text{ mole}^{-1}$	
Na ⁺	16.51
K ⁺	16.34
Cs ⁺	16.40
NH ₄ ⁺	16.45
(5) $M(\phi^{\circ}MI - \phi^{\circ}MNO_3)/cm^3 \text{ mole}^{-1}$	
Na ⁺	7.71
K ⁺	7.29
NH ₄ ⁺	7.75
(6) $M(\phi^{\circ}MNO_3 - \phi^{\circ}MBr)/cm^3 \text{ mole}^{-1}$	
Na ⁺	8.80
K ⁺	9.05
NH ₄ ⁺	8.70

The almost constant values of the differences ($\phi^{\circ}_{AX} - \phi^{\circ}_{BX}$) for different anions (X = Br⁻, I⁻, NO₃⁻) and that of ($\phi^{\circ}_{MX} - \phi^{\circ}_{MY}$) for different cations (M = Na⁺, K⁺, Cs,

NH₄⁺), indicates that the ϕ° values are additive in DMSO as in other solvents of high dielectric constant namely water², formamide³ and NMP⁴. This indicates that at infinite dilution the apparent ionic volume of each ion tends to a definite limiting value at a particular temperature, independent of the effect of opposite ions present in the solution. Thus we may write

$$\phi^{\circ}_{MX} = \phi^{\circ}_{M+} + \phi^{\circ}_{X-}$$

Thus the selected values of the difference in the limiting ionic volumes of two ions for different set of ions given in table 2 can be used to evaluate individual limiting ionic volumes for different ions, if the value for any one of these ions is known; although it is not possible at present. The attempts will be made to evaluate ϕ° (ion) in the next communication.

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Studies on the Binding of Hg(II) with Casein using Mercury Electrode.

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THE binding of metal ion with proteins has been studied by potentiometric¹⁻⁴, polarographic⁵⁻⁸ and equilibrium dialysis⁹⁻¹² methods. Similar studies with Hg(II) ions have not been reported so far. The later two methods could not be used due to some inherent experimental difficulties and, therefore first method was attempted for these determinations. This communication reports the result on Hg(II)-casein interaction by potentiometry using mercury electrode¹³. The results so obtained were compared with the pH metric method.

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